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Reinforcement of alkali-activated cements based matrices using olive pruning fibres as an alternative to traditional fibres

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ABSTRACT

Recent research has focused on the development of environmentally sustainable materials for replacing conventional Portland cement. Alkali-activated cements, derived from aluminosilicate-rich precursors and an alkaline activator, have been a key area of interest. However, the properties of these materials vary with different precursors, leading to issues like shrinkage and flexural strength deficiencies. To address these challenges, scientists have explored the reinforcement of alkali-activated materials through the incorporation of fibres, both synthetic and natural.

This study involved a comparative analysis of various fibres, including synthetic options such as polypropylene and glass fibres, as well as natural fibres like sisal, cellulose, and olive pruning fibres, with some subjected to specific treatments. A consistent 1% wt. fibre content was maintained, as determined optimal in prior research. The matrix was formed using electric arc furnace slag (EAFS) and biomass bottom ash (BBA) as raw materials, while an activator solution of KOH and K_2SiO_3 was used. Mechanical, physical, and thermal properties were evaluated. The results demonstrated that natural fibres improved flexural strength up to 20% and increased the ductility of the matrix, but the addition of fibres negatively affected physical and thermal properties. Compression strength had different behaviour, improving values in the case of use olive pruning fibres treated by K_2SiO_3 solution or cellulose commercial fibres, up to 9 and 15%. This research highlights the potential of natural fibres to enhance specific properties of alkali-activated materials.

1. Introduction

Materials engineering is in continuous development of new environmentally-friendly materials. In the case of construction materials, it is well-known that traditional Portland cement generates significant CO_2 emissions. Consequently, there is an abundance of research aimed at partially or completely replacing conventional Portland cement. Alkali-activated cements stand out as one of the most promising alternatives to replace Portland cement. These cements are the product of a chemical reaction between highly alkaline solutions and silicoaluminates, which can be of natural origin (such as clays) or synthetic (like industrial by-products), with varying levels of calcium content. Alkali-activated cements are notable for their exceptional mechanical strength and impressive resistance to a wide range of chemical and physical challenges. Notably, their production process does not demand the substantial energy consumption associated with the traditional manufacturing of Portland cement (Torres-Carrasco and Puertas, 2017).

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Research efforts have been focused on enhancing the properties of alkali-activated cements, which have demonstrated promising results. Despite the positive outcomes achieved, these materials exhibit issues related to shrinkage and flexural strength (Santana et al., 2021). Other reasons for the incorporation of fibres in alkaline activated materials include the reduction of cracking. To counteract these issues, numerous research studies have emerged aimed at reinforcing the matrix of alkali-activated cements through the use of fibres (Chen et al., 2021; Feng et al., 2023; Maoujoud et al., 2023). The fibres mentioned in the literature have been both synthetic and natural origin (Abdalla et al., 2023), although some authors introduce another category known as "inorganic fibres" to distinguish them from other synthetic fibres (Li et al., 2023). Synthetic fibres are organic fibres that undergo a sintering process (Li et al., 2023). Some of the synthetic fibres used in composites include polyester fibres, polypropylene fibres, polyvinyl alcohol fibres (PVA), polyacrylonitrile fibres (PAN), and aramid fibres (Zhang et al., 2021; Aisheh et al., 2022; Haily et al., 2023). On the other hand, inorganic fibres are derived from mineral materials, with notable examples including glass fibres, basalt fibres, ceramic fibres, carbon fibres, and steel fibres (Li et al., 2023).

When it comes to natural fibres, there is a wide variety, with notable examples including cotton, sisal, abaca, coconut, rice straw, flax, and bamboo (Santana et al., 2021; Haily et al., 2023). Due to the extensive range of natural fibres, other authors categorize them into wood and non-wood fibres, and based on the plant part they originate from (Jawaid and Khalil, 2011; Ardanuy et al., 2015). The most intriguing natural fibres for use as reinforcement are those that consist of a significant amount of cellulose (Acharya et al., 2023).

Furthermore, to enhance the properties of fibres, physical or chemical treatments can be applied. These treatments aim to improve the fibre-matrix interaction by roughening the fibre surface. There are numerous treatments available, some of which include mercerization (Rahman et al., 2023), hornification (Claramunt et al., 2011), silane treatment (Li et al., 2007), acetylation (Ouarhim et al., 2019), benzoilation (Mohammed et al., 2022), among others treatments.

The results of different fibres depend on their origin, size, morphology, and the matrix they are embedded in. As a result, it can be observed varying outcomes. According to Ranjbar and Zhang (2020), the mechanical strength of geopolymers depends among other factors on brittleness, pore structure and microcrack distribution. Wongsa et al. (2020) compared composites reinforced with natural fibres and glass fibre at different inclusion percentages in geopolymer mortar based on fly ash. The results showed that natural fibres (coconut and sisal) outperformed synthetic fibres due to their excellent fibre-matrix interaction. Flexural strength values ranged from 3.7 to 6.6 MPa when using fibres glass and natural fibres as reinforcement, respectively. However, the trend of flexural strength improvement was not consistent in the study conducted by Korniejenko et al. (2016). Haily et al. (2023) achieved similar flexural strengths in composites reinforced with pine cone fibres and fibres glass but observed different compressive strengths, with pine cone fibres experiencing less loss of strength.

Mixtures of fibres have also been employed to reinforce cementitious matrices. Naraganti et al. (2019) used combinations of steel-sisal and steel-polypropylene fibres and found better initial crack resistance for sisal fibres compared to synthetic polypropylene fibres. There is a substantial body of literature on the use of various fibres, both synthetic and natural, highlighting the significance of natural fibres due to their cost-effectiveness and availability (Ahmad et al., 2023), showcasing their potential for use alongside structural materials (Abdalla et al., 2023). On the other hand, there are few works found in the literature in which KOH has been used as an alkaline activator in alkaline cements with the simultaneous presence of natural fibres. According to Bakthavatchalam and Rajendran (2021), among other advantages, the lower viscosity of KOH leads to higher strength, better durability, associated with lower shrinkage and porosity. This type of activators, according to Hosan et al. (2016), exhibit fewer surface cracks than Na-based activators.

The aim of this study is to compare the performance of untreated and treated olive pruning fibres with traditional synthetic and natural fibres used in other materials as reinforcements in alkali-activated cements based on 50 wt % electric arc furnace slag (EAFS) – 50 wt % biomass bottom ash (BBA). Another objective of this work was to address the suitability of KOH and K_2SiO_3 for use as an alkaline activator in alkaline cements. The synthetic fibres used were Polypropylene (PP) and fibreglass (FG). Additionally, sisal and commercial cellulose were employed as natural fibres. The olive pruning fibres were used both untreated and treated with various treatments: 5% wt. NaOH (mercerization), 10 wt % Na_2SiO_3 , 3 wt % $CaCl_2$, 6 wt % silane, hornification (dry-wet cycles), and a combination of mercerization and ultrasounds. The quantity of fibres (1 wt %) used in the alkali-activated material matrix was fixed for all composites manufactured. This percentage was determined in previous studies as the optimal proportion for the precursors employed.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw materials

2.1.1. Fibres as reinforcement

In the present study, treated and untreated olive pruning fibres were employed as reinforcement for alkali-activated cements based on electric arc furnace slag (EAFS) and biomass bottom ash (BBA). These fibres were compared to four commercial fibres: two of synthetic origin and two of natural origin.

The synthetic fibres used in this study were polypropylene (PP) fibres and glass fibres (GF). The properties of these fibres are detailed in Table 1. The PP fibres were supplied by Geotex S.A. (Spain), and the GF by Aeroepoxy Composites Andalucía S.L. (Spain).

The commercial and natural fibres included sisal (Sis) and cellulose (Cel). Their properties and chemical composition are detailed in Tables 1 and Table 2 respectively. It is worth noting the high cellulose content of the commercial cellulose fibres, which, according to previous studies, would favour an increase in flexural strength (Dhasindrakrishna et al., 2023).

Table 1
Synthetic fibres properties.

	PP	GF	Sisal	Cellulose Arboce®	Olive pruning fibres
Density (g/m^3)	0.91	1.90	1.66	1.00	1.35
Diameter (μm)	45	85	200	35	175
Length (mm)	4 \pm 0.5	4 \pm 0.5	4 \pm 0.5	0.5 \pm 0.05	0.84 \pm 0.5
Tensile strength (MPa)	300–400	1000	350–500	–	–

Table 2
Chemical composition of natural fibres (% wt.).

	Sisal	Cellulose Arboce®	Olive pruning fibres
Cellulose	78.11	90	33.83
Hemicellulose	10.63	0	21.65
Lignine	8.50	0	28.27
Ash	1.59	10.00	5.11
Others	1.17	0.00	11.13

The cellulose fibres used as reinforcement were supplied by J. Rettenmaier & Söhne – JRS (Germany) under the trade name Arboce® PWC 500. These fibres had an average length of 0.5 mm and a diameter of 35 μm . Meanwhile, the sisal fibres were provided by Cayetano García del Moral S.L. (Spain). These fibres had a diameter of 200 μm and an average length of 4 mm.

The chemical composition of the olive pruning fibres is presented in Table 2. These fibres were crushed and sieved to obtain a range between 125 and 250 μm . Subsequently, the average size of these fibres was determined using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), revealing dimensions of 840 μm in length and 175 μm in diameter (Table 1). The olive pruning fibres were used as both treated and untreated (OUT) reinforcements.

The treated olive fibres underwent various treatments (Table 3) to enhance their compatibility with the matrix. These treatments involved immersing the fibres in different chemical solutions or humidity-drying cycles (see Table 3). The chemical solutions used were as follows: 10 wt % Na_2SiO_3 , 3 wt % $CaCl_2$, 5 wt % NaOH (a process known as mercerization), and 6 wt % silane (3-aminopropylmethyldiethoxysilane) in distilled water, identified as ONS, OC, OM, and OSil, respectively. The fibres were immersed in these solutions for 60 min with agitation, followed by rinsing to achieve a neutral pH. They were then dried and stored for later use. In the case of hornification process, OH5 and OH10, the fibres were subjected to 5 and 10 cycles, respectively, with the following procedure: 60 min of immersion in distilled water with agitation, drying in an oven at 80 °C. Once dried, they were stored for later use. The OMU treatment (mercerization-ultrasound) consists of two parts: first, the fibres underwent a mercerization treatment (similar to OM) for 30 min, and then they were subjected to ultrasonic treatment for 30 min (US). After completing both processes, the fibres were washed with distilled water to achieve a neutral pH, dried in an oven, and stored for later use.

2.1.2. Precursors and activator

For the production of alkali-activated cements, EAFS and BBA were used as precursor materials. The optimal 50-50 wt % ratio, as established in previous studies (Gómez-Casero et al., 2021), was reinforced (Table 4). The EAFS (Electric Arc Furnace Slag) was obtained from the refining process in the steel production from scrap at the Siderúrgica Sevillana S.A. factory (Spain). In the case of BBA (Biomass Bottom Ash), it was derived from the energy generation plant of Aldebarán Energía del Guadalquivir (Spain), following the combustion of biomass, including olive pruning and forest waste.

Table 3
Treatments on olive pruning fibres.

	Solution	Time (min)	Cycles
ONS	10 wt % Na_2SiO_3	60	1
OC	3 wt % $CaCl_2$	60	1
OM	5 wt % NaOH	60	1
OSil	6 wt % Silane	60	1
OH5	Water	60 per cycle	5
OH10	Water	60 per cycle	10
OMU	5% NaOH + US	30 + 30	1 + 1

Table 4
Composition of composites manufactured (g).

	EAFS	BBA	Fibres	Activator solution
Control paste	225	225	–	270
Composites reinforced	222.75	222.75	4.5	270

The EAFS was supplied with a maximum size of 4 mm, while the BBA had a maximum size of 8 mm. Both materials were crushed to achieve a maximum particle size of 100 μm . Additionally, both materials achieved a particle size close to 22 μm for EAFS and 30 μm for BBA.

The chemical composition and crystalline phases were determined in previous studies as well (Gómez-Casero et al., 2021). EAFS is primarily composed of CaO (30.89%), Fe_2O_3 (24.16 %), and SiO_2 (17.29 %), while BBA consists of SiO_2 (33.88 %), CaO (26.17 %), and K_2O (11.16 %). As for the predominant crystalline phases, EAFS contains primarily wuestite, larnite, and gehlenite, while BBA is mainly composed of quartz, calcite, and lime.

The alkaline activator used was optimized in previous works (Gómez-Casero et al., 2021). The activator consisted of a mixture 50 wt % KOH (8 M) and 50 wt % K_2SiO_3 , obtaining a Ms ratio ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{K}_2\text{O}$) of 0.89. KOH was provided by GlobalChem (85% of purity) and K_2SiO_3 supplied by Roth company (composition by weight: 7.5–8.7% K_2O , 19.5–21.8% SiO_2 and 69.5–73% H_2O). The liquid/binder ratio was maintained for all specimens at 0.6.

2.2. Binder manufacturing

The procedure followed for the fabrication of the composites was as follows: First, the precursor materials and fibres were mixed in a planetary mixer for 90 s to ensure a homogeneous blend. Next, the activator was poured, and mixing continued for an additional 90 s. The container walls were cleaned with the aid of a spatula and mixed for another 30 s. After this time, the fresh material was poured into the moulds. For mechanical testing and physical property evaluation, steel prismatic moulds of dimensions 60x10x10 mm were used. For thermal conductivity testing, plastic cylindrical moulds with a diameter of 55 mm and a height of 15 mm were employed. The moulds with the fresh paste were subjected to 60 strokes on a flow table to remove any trapped air bubbles, and then stored in a climate chamber at 20 °C and 90% humidity for 24 h. After this curing period, the specimens were demoulded and further stored under the same conditions until the testing age, which was set at 1, 7, 28, or 90 days.

Mechanical properties were determined in accordance with the UNE-EN 1015–11:2000/A1:2007 standard (EN 1015-11, 2007) at 1, 7, 28, and 90 days of curing. An MTS Insight 5 machine and MTS 8101 machine were used for flexural strength and compressive strength testing, respectively. Physical properties were assessed at 1, 7, and 28 days following the UNE-EN 1015–10 standard (EN 1015-10, 2020). Thermal conductivity was determined at 28 days of curing following the ISO 8302 standard (ISO-8302, 1991) using a FOX 50 TA Instruments heat flow meter.

Additional techniques were employed to characterize selected fibres and composites: Attenuated Total Reflectance – Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) using a Vertex 70 Bruker in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) using an Empyrean equipment with a PIXcel-3D detector from PANalytical were used to powder from compression samples, and Scanning Electron Microscopy – Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) with a JEAL model SM 840 in flexural strength samples at 28 days of curing.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mechanical properties

3.1.1. Flexural strength

The effect of incorporating fibres into the alkali-activated cement matrix is presented in Fig. 1. All the fibres increased the flexural strength of the composite due to the sewing effect (bridge effect) in the microcracks developed in the matrix, preventing their propagation (Zhao et al., 2023; Chindasiriphan et al., 2023). Synthetic fibres showed a certain improvement in flexural strength, increasing by 13% and 14% for PP and GF, respectively, at 90 days of curing, compared to the control sample. Regarding natural fibres, cellulose fibres achieved a 27% increase, while sisal fibres exhibited only a 7% increase in flexural strength at 90 days of curing. Olive pruning

Fig. 1. Flexural strength as a function of fibre types and curing times.

fibres also achieved values higher than the control sample, both for treated and untreated fibres, except in the OM and OMU samples, where the values were equivalent to the control sample. The treatment that yielded the best results was carried out with a Na_2SiO_3 solution (ONS), increasing flexural strength by 43%. The OC and OM samples also exceeded the control sample, both with around a 30% increase. The OH5 and OH10 samples achieved a 21% and 24% increase in strength, respectively. Therefore, most of the treatments applied to the olive pruning fibres had a positive effect on the flexural strength of the composite. One of the factors contributing to the mechanical strength of composite materials is the interaction between the fibre and the matrix. In this case, the treatments applied to the olive pruning fibres have enhanced the cohesive force with the geopolymeric matrix. This behaviour is most likely due to the fact that the surface of these fibres is quite rough as a result of the pre-treatments they underwent. These results are consistent with those obtained by other authors who used alkaline solutions and heat treatments to enhance the fibre-matrix interaction in alkali-activated materials (Yan et al., 2012; Malenab et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2021). This is because in the presence of reinforcing fibres, the rate of crack initiation and propagation gradually decreases (Maoujoud et al., 2023).

The better performance of natural fibres compared to synthetic fibres can be attributed to differences in surface roughness of the fibres (Xiao et al., 2022) (discussed in section 3.6). In fact, fibres treated with alkaline solutions achieved better results due to an increase in cellulose content resulting from the removal of other compounds and an increase in the contact surface area of the fibre (Dhasindrakrishna et al., 2023; Feng et al., 2023).

The effect of alkali treatment on natural fibres involves the dissolution of hemicellulose, while the content of cellulose and lignin remains relatively constant (Wang et al., 2012). It can be inferred that since the combined content of cellulose and lignin in olive pruning fibres exceeds 60%, they are responsible for the mechanical strength. In the case of cellulose, the alkaline medium breaks glycosidic bonds, influencing the degree of polymerization and reducing crystallinity by breaking intermolecular hydrogen bonds (Torres-Fuentes and Fernández-Urquiza, 2016), making it more amorphous, and thus less rigid and more elastic. This imparts greater deformability before rupture, explaining why they tend to exhibit a ductile fracture type, resulting in tougher materials. Specifically, it is the stronger alkali treatments, such as ONS, that have yielded better results in terms of flexural strength.

In the case of PP and GF, it was observed (see 3.6 section) that the fibres kept the specimen intact after fracture, indicating a transition from brittle fracture to ductile fracture (Zhao et al., 2023). This behaviour has been reported in other studies (He et al., 2023). Additionally, it could be seen that the fibres were pulled out of the matrix, detaching from it before breaking. This occurs because synthetic fibres have high tensile strength but may not fully utilize that strength due to their smooth surface, leading to reduced interaction with the matrix (Mrduljaš et al., 2023). Despite not yielding the best results, they can still be an interesting alternative due to their low cost and chemical stability (Li et al., 2023).

It can be observed that fibres have the potential to reduce the development and propagation of fractures when high loads are applied to the developed composite materials (Chen et al., 2021), thereby increasing the tensile strength and ductility of the material (Nazar et al., 2023). It can be seen in Fig. 2 that olive pruning fibres increase the ductility of the composite, and a greater increase occurs when these fibres are treated with sodium silicate. However, commercial fibres (synthetic and cellulose fibres) do not modify the ductility of the composite significantly, although they do increase its flexural strength.

3.1.2. Compressive strength

The results of the compressive strength of alkali-activated cements reinforced with fibres are shown in Fig. 3. Consistent with other studies, the addition of fibres generally results in a decrease in compressive strength (Li et al., 2017). However, there are two cases in which compressive strength improved compared to the control sample. These are the composites reinforced with cellulose and olive pruning fibres treated with sodium silicate. In both cases, the strength increased by 15% and 9% at 90 days of curing, respectively. In the rest of the specimens, compressive strength decreased by 5%–21%. The most significant decrease occurred with untreated olive pruning fibres and those treated with CaCl_2 . This result contrasts with the flexural strength results, as the CaCl_2 treatment significantly improved flexural strength compared to the unreinforced control sample.

The loss of compressive strength in synthetic fibres of PP and GF was 6% in both cases. This decrease, which is less than that observed in untreated olive pruning fibres, may be related to the ability of synthetic fibres to absorb stress, prevent or delay the formation of microcracks, or reduce porosity, among other factors (Nazar et al., 2023). These fibres act as support or bridges, delaying or

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curves of different composites at 28 days of curing.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength as a function of fibre types and curing times.

preventing the development of microcracks (He et al., 2023). Another explanation could be the difference in fibre length. Synthetic fibres had a greater average length than olive pruning fibres, which helps to distribute the load and improve stress transfer through the fibre (Zhao et al., 2023).

The decrease in compressive strength of alkali-activated binders reinforced with PP and GF fibres is attributed to the morphology of these fibres, which can slide under tensile stress (Nazar et al., 2023). They are unable to fully utilize their high tensile strength, leading to an inefficient transfer of stresses, which negatively affects the flexural and compressive strength of the composites.

The decrease in compressive strength of olive pruning fibres (except those treated with sodium silicate) can be attributed to their lower elastic modulus compared to the matrix (Li et al., 2017). In the case of ONS, the improvement can also be attributed to the release of residual sodium silicate used in the prior treatment of the fibres, which increases the generation of C-(A)-S-H gel (Ntimugura et al., 2023).

The improvement in compressive strength in composites reinforced with cellulose fibres may be due to a reduction in water-to-binder ratio because these small-sized fibres can absorb water (Chen et al., 2021). They gradually release water, hydrating the matrix over time. The increase in compressive strength with the reinforcement of commercial cellulose fibres has been previously documented by Ye et al. (2018).

The gain in strength was more significant in flexural strength compared to compressive strength due to the tensile strength capacity of the fibres relative to the cement matrix (Dhasindrakrishna et al., 2023). In the case of synthetic fibres, despite having higher tensile strength capacity, they achieved worse results in flexural strength due to their lower fibre-matrix interaction.

3.1.3. Ratio of flexural strength to compressive strength

The relationships between flexural strength and compressive strength were analysed as a function of curing time with the different reinforcing fibres, as shown in Fig. 4. The values for the control samples exhibited a decreasing trend, indicating that the development

Fig. 4. Flexural strength to compressive strength ratio at 90 days of curing.

of flexural strength was slower than the development of compressive strength over time (Chen et al., 2021). This same trend was observed in the addition of different fibres, with some values being lower at early ages. The highest degree of toughness at 90 days of curing was found for the olive pruning fibres treated with CaCl_2 , although, as discussed in the previous section, their compressive strength decreased by 24%. This could be because it negatively impacts the loss of continuity due to the presence of pores and fibres in the geopolymeric gel matrix (which, as will be seen later, results in lower composite density) more than the increase in stress generated by the fibre-matrix interaction. Consequently, it is found that the addition of these types of natural fibres has the effect of increasing the toughness and ductility of the composites, at the expense of reducing their compressive strength.

3.2. Physical properties

The physical properties of the different fibre-reinforced composites are presented in Fig. 5 as a function of curing time. The bulk density decreased with the incorporation of fibres. This decrease is attributed to the difference in density between the precursor materials and the reinforcing fibres.

The decrease was more significant in synthetic fibres at shorter curing times. At longer curing times, the values of the commercial fibres, except for PP fibres, equalled or exceeded the values of the control paste. All fibre-reinforced composites with olive pruning fibres showed values close to the control at early curing ages, but at later ages, they exhibited lower values. This trend is caused by the fact that fibres accumulate activator liquid/solution at early ages, which is released during the curing process, leading to the formation of porosity (Wongsa et al., 2020). Although this can also be attributed to the degradation of hemicellulose into other polysaccharides.

Composites reinforced with PP fibres consistently showed lower values throughout the curing process. The significant decrease in the bulk density of these composites is due to the low density of the PP fibres (0.9 g/dm^3) and the high mass percentage of fibre incorporation, which represents a large volume of fibres. The high volume fraction of PP fibres increased the viscosity of the fresh paste, leading to fibre agglomeration and bubble retention during the mixing process (Haily et al., 2023). However, they exhibit a high tensile strength. Therefore, despite having a low density, these samples achieve high flexural strength values, exceeding the Control paste. On the other hand, composites reinforced with cellulose fibres achieved higher densification, primarily due to their high cellulose content (Ye et al., 2018), contributing to the increase in flexural strength. In addition, after 28 days of curing, all samples increase their apparent density values due to the formation of a higher amount of geopolymeric gel in the matrix.

The apparent porosity and water absorption showed different behaviours depending on the type of fibre used. In the case of the control sample, it followed the trend found in a previous study (Gómez-Casero et al., 2021), with the highest value observed at 7 days of curing, decreasing to 9.2% and 4.8% at 28 days of curing for apparent porosity and water absorption, respectively. Commercial fibres, at early ages, had very high values, but at longer curing periods, these values decreased and even improved compared to the control paste. This behaviour of absorbing more water/solution at early ages hindered the hydration of the paste but reduced the porosity of the cement (Feng et al., 2023). The best values were obtained in cements reinforced with cellulose fibres (Cel), achieving 7.7 % apparent porosity and 4 % water absorption at 28 days of curing. This behaviour has been reported by other authors, attributed to the small diameter of these fibres (microfibres) (Nazar et al., 2023). When PP fibres are used, a decrease in apparent porosity and water absorption is obtained at long curing periods. The composites reinforced with olive pruning fibres had the highest values. The differences in the average diameter between commercial fibres and olive pruning fibres also affected the formation of voids around the fibres (Chakilam and Cui, 2020) as well as the absorption capacity of the natural fibres (Poletanovic et al., 2020).

Greater water absorption implies poorer hydration of the matrix, which can explain the poorer development of strengths as empty voids are generated in the matrix due to the evaporation of the water contained in them (Xiao et al., 2022). However, in the case of ONS, despite achieving high porosity and absorption, the mechanical strength is greater than the control sample, as explained earlier, due to the formation of a higher amount of gel.

3.3. Thermal conductivity

The thermal conductivity values in fibre-reinforced composites ranged between 0.606 and 0.798 W/mK (Fig. 6). Values decrease when fibres are added. In addition, these results are consistent with the physical properties described earlier. Generally, it is observed that thermal conductivity values tend to decrease as porosity increases and density decreases in the composites, which is in line with findings from other studies (Wongsa et al., 2020; Hamada et al., 2023). As indicated by Abbas et al. (2023) the composite materials become more porous with the inclusion of the fibres, which generate an increase in trapped air pockets after the addition of the fibres in the fresh geopolymer paste. This behaviour has also been observed in geopolymers formulated with natural fibres (Yanou et al., 2021).

However, the composites reinforced with commercial fibres exhibited a different behaviour, as they achieved density and porosity values similar to the unreinforced paste but managed to reduce the thermal conductivity values compared to the unreinforced paste. This could be attributed to the inherently lower thermal conductivity of the fibres in comparison to the cement matrix (Zhao et al., 2023). The thermal insulation capability of composites reinforcement by olive pruning fibres, which had lower density values and higher porosity compared to the other composites, also contributed to their lower thermal conductivity. It is worth noting that the formation of air bubbles during the mixing process can influence the thermal conductivity of the composites, as these air bubbles act as an additional thermal insulator (Hamada et al., 2023). Samples reinforced with treated olive fibres obtain lower thermal conductivity values because they exhibit higher apparent porosity than samples reinforced with untreated olive fibres.

Fig. 5. Physical properties of composites manufactured: a) Bulk density, b) Apparent porosity, and c) Water absorption.

3.4. Functional groups analysis over olive pruning fibres

The purpose of the treatments applied to the olive pruning fibre was to eliminate lignin, hemicellulose, and other impurities, with the aim of achieving a degraded and rough surface. This surface modification enhances the fibre-matrix interaction, thereby improving the mechanical strength of the composite (Ntimugura et al., 2023). In Fig. 7, the modifications brought about by each of the treatments on the olive pruning fibres in the FTIR spectra can be observed. Generally, these treatments led to a decrease in hydrogen bonds in the hydroxyl group, which is present in cellulose and hemicellulose. This reduction is associated with the decrease in the band centred at 3335 cm^{-1} (Phiri et al., 2023), indicating the removal of part of these compounds.

Fig. 6. Thermal conductivity results at 28 days of curing.

Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of olive pruning fibres treated and untreated.

Two bands centred at 2919 and 2850 cm^{-1} , characteristic of C–H bonds in lignin, tend to decrease in intensity or even disappear due to the treatments (Özçimen and Ersoy-Meriçboyu, 2010), indicating the disappearance of lignin in the fibre. The band centred at 1732 cm^{-1} , associated with hemicellulose, also decreases in intensity. This demonstrates the removal of a portion of the hemicellulose in the treated fibres (Li et al., 2017). The C=C bonds in lignin are also affected by the treatments, as indicated by a wavenumber shift from 1617 to 1595 cm^{-1} (de Souza Castoldi et al., 2023).

The bands centred at 1595 and 1422 cm^{-1} in untreated fibres, also associated with lignin, undergo less modification with the treatments, in line with other authors (Hoareau et al., 2004). At 1233 cm^{-1} , there is a band associated with C–O and C–C bonds, present in cellulose and hemicellulose. This band decreases with the treatments, with a significant reduction observed when the fibres are treated with NaOH, indicating a greater degradation of the fibre with this treatment. The peak centred at 1025 cm^{-1} in untreated fibres, associated with C–O and C–C bonds present in cellulose and hemicellulose (Akinyemi et al., 2020), experiences a shift to 1030 cm^{-1} due to their removal through the application of the treatments.

3.5. XRD analysis

X-ray diffraction analysis (DRX) was performed on the best specimens (Fig. 8). After the incorporation of the fibres, no changes in the crystalline phases are observed, indicating that there are no changes in the hydration products. This is in line with other studies (He et al., 2023).

The main hydration product in the matrix coincides with previous works, showing a halo between 20 and 40° 2θ, indicating the formation of geopolymeric gel (Gómez-Casero et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022). The diffraction peak at 29.36° is also intensified, associated with CASH gel and calcite (Gómez-Casero et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2016), indicating matrix carbonation.

3.6. Microstructural analysis

In SEM images, differences between fibres of different origins are noticeable (see Fig. 9). Synthetic fibres exhibited a smooth surface and a homogeneous cross-section, whereas natural fibres had a less smooth surface. Additionally, olive pruning fibres displayed a very rough surface after the chemical and physical treatments.

Untreated olive fibres exhibited longitudinally oriented microfibrils, bound by layers of hemicellulose and lignin. However, these treated fibres changed their longitudinal appearance, showing greater surface degradation as a result of the treatments. The treatments removed part of the lignin and hemicellulose from the fibres, causing the separation of fibrils, resulting in a rougher surface (de Souza Castoldi et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2016; Wongsu et al., 2020; Li et al., 2017). This change in fibre morphology results in improved fibre-matrix adhesion and enhanced energy dissipation during composite failure due to a larger fibre failure surface (Li et al., 2017).

The control paste (Fig. 10) exhibited a dense and homogeneous matrix due to the formation of geopolymeric gel and C-A-S-H gel (points 1 and 2) (Wongsa et al., 2020). Unreacted particles of both precursors (points 3 and 4) and shrinkage-induced microcracks resulting from the evaporation of water during the curing process were also observed.

In the SEM images, the effective fibre-matrix interaction of all the fibres used as reinforcement in the alkali-activated cement matrix is evident (Fig. 11). This interaction is identifiable as hydration products from the matrix are observed on the surface of the fibres (Li et al., 2017; Akinyemi et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2021; Xiao et al., 2022). In this regard, natural fibres show a higher fibre-matrix interaction since they have a greater amount of matrix hydration products on their surface, with olive pruning fibres showing the most significant presence.

Moreover, depending on the type of fibre, the composites exhibited different failure mechanisms. Composites reinforced with synthetic fibres, which have high flexural strength and a smooth surface, displayed a "pull-out" behaviour (Fig. 11d). Conversely, those reinforced with sisal and olive fibres mostly showed fibre fracture (Fig. 11b and c). Composites reinforced with cellulose fibres exhibited a combination of both behaviours (Fig. 11a). These different behaviours are a result of distinct energy absorption mechanisms (Ardanuy et al., 2015). Indeed, the different behaviours of the fibres are also reflected in the ductility of composites, as described in the stress-strain curves (Fig. 2). Thus, the geopolymers to which PP and cellulose fibres have been added, corresponding to Fig. 11a

Fig. 8. XRD spectra of composites at 28 days of curing.

Fig. 9. Natural fibres SEM images: a) Cellulose fibres, b) Olive pruning fibres untreated, c) Olive pruning fibres treated by Na_2SiO_3 solution.

and d, have stress-strain curves in which it can be seen that they have a lower breaking strain, but are more ductile. This is a consequence of the fact that the fibres pull out and slide on the matrix but do not fracture, making them more ductile and tenacious.

The combination of failure mechanisms and the good adhesion of natural fibres, particularly cellulose fibres (Cel) and olive pruning fibres treated with sodium silicate (ONS), explain their superior mechanical performance (flexural and compressive strength) (Silva et al., 2020). It can also be observed that the alkali matrix did not cause degradation of the commercial fibres. However, the olive pruning fibres experienced aging due to contact with the alkaline matrix, resulting in the generation of voids in the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) and a subsequent decrease in compressive strength. This decrease was not noticeable in fibres treated with sodium silicate, as these fibres released residual treatment solution that aided in the geopolymerization of the matrix, counteracting the negative effects of fibre aging (as mentioned earlier). Some other authors attribute the generation of these voids to the effect of specimen fracture during mechanical strength testing or during specimen preparation for SEM observation (Akinoyemi et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2021).

4. Conclusions

Different types of fibres, both synthetic and natural, were compared by manufacturing composites reinforced with polypropylene fibre, fibre glass, sisal fibre, commercial cellulose fibre, and treated and untreated olive pruning fibres. The results revealed clear differences based on the nature of the fibres.

- All the fibres improved or matched the flexural strength values of the unreinforced control sample, with olive fibres treated with a chemical solution of sodium silicate achieving the best results. Commercial cellulose fibres also showed a high percentage of improvement compared to the control sample. Synthetic fibres achieved higher flexural strength values compared to the control sample. However, these fibres did not exhibit the same adhesion to the matrix as natural fibres. Therefore, despite having higher tensile strength, they could not fully utilize it, as they tended to detach from the matrix. Differences are due to fibre surface.
- The compressive strength values decreased with the addition of fibres, except for the cements reinforced with olive fibres treated with sodium silicate and commercial cellulose fibres. These composites exceeded the compressive strength of the control sample at 90 days due to good fibre-matrix interaction and matrix densification. The reason is the release of residual treatment solution in olive pruning fibres and the alkaline activator retained in cellulose fibres.

Fig. 10. Control paste SEM image at 28 days of curing, without reinforcement.

- Concerning physical properties, synthetic fibres had lower density values at early ages due to their lower density and lower water absorption capacity, preventing the formation of water-filled spaces that can lead to the development of pores upon water evaporation. Hence, at 28 days, they achieved values similar to the control sample, except for polypropylene fibres, which have very low density. Treated and untreated olive fibres maintained stable values over time. However, water absorption was higher in treated fibres due to surface degradation, resulting in the generation of more spaces to retain water. Composites reinforced with treated olive pruning fibres showed lower apparent porosity, as geopolymeric and C-A-S-H gel formed on the fibre surface, covering the spaces generated during chemical treatment degradation. This gel deposited on the fibre surfaces was verified through SEM micrographs.
- Thermal conductivity followed the trend found in physical properties. Even with similar density values, the nature of the fibres influenced the results. Synthetic fibres enhanced the insulating capacity of the composites reinforced with these fibres. While olive pruning fibres decreased conductivity values when they were treated.
- FTIR analysis revealed that primarily hemicellulose and lignin were removed from the fibre surface of olive pruning fibres treated, making it rougher and increasing the contact surface with the alkali-activated cement matrix. Thus the fibre-matrix adhesion was improved and this behaviour had impact over mechanical properties.
- The addition of fibres did not alter the phases found in the alkali-activated cement matrix, as no new phases appeared, nor did existing ones disappear in the control sample.
- SEM analysis showed the degradation of the surface of olive fibres treated with various chemical and physical treatments. Moreover, the alkaline nature of the matrix did not deteriorate the fibres over time. Micrograph showed different behaviour in fibre breakage, showing synthetic fibres not break but they pull out from matrix. In the case of olive fibres break, leaving a part in the matrix.

In conclusion, better results can be obtained in alkali-activated cements when they are reinforced with fibres. Furthermore, natural fibres exhibit superior interaction with the matrix, especially when treated. These treatments are more effective when the cellulose content in the treated fibre is higher. Therefore, commercial fibres with a high cellulose content are also a viable option. Both treated and commercial natural fibres are sustainable and cost-effective alternatives for improving the properties of alkali-activated cements, making them more competitive with traditional Portland cement used in the construction industry.

Fig. 11. SEM images and back-scattered electro images of composites reinforced, at 28 days of curing. with: a) Cellulose, b) OUT c) ONS, and d) PP.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

M.A. Gómez-Casero: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **L. Pérez-Villarejo:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **E. Castro:** Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **D. Eliche-Quesada:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Fig. 11. (continued)

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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